

Advances in mineral carbonation
science and technology for
production of construction materials

Lecture 1 – The Bigger Picture

Ruben Snellings, KU Leuven, Belgium
ASCENT Summer School, Zlarin

[The Blue Marble, NASA, 1972]

The bigger picture – the carbon cycle

- The short cycle
 - Atmosphere, biosphere and hydrosphere
 - Large fluxes, small reservoirs

[numbers in Gt C per year, number in parentheses in Gt C; source NASA Earth Observatory]

The slow carbonate-silicate cycle

- Long cycle
 - Lithosphere
 - Small fluxes, large reservoirs
 - $CaSiO_3 + CO_2 \leftrightarrow CaCO_3 + SiO_2$

[numbers in Gt C per year, number in parentheses in Gt C; source: Kasting, 2019; Hilton & West, 2020]

Feedback mechanisms

- Silicate weathering reactions are slow – how to accelerate them?
 - pH: more rapid dissolution in acid, in case of some minerals as well in alkaline solutions, (depends on basicity of the mineral)
 - Temperature: higher temperature leads to more rapid dissolution
 - Creation of more reactive surface area
 - Use of more reactive minerals or phases

[Gudbrandsson et al. 2014; Gislason & Oelkers, 2003]

Mineral carbonation as a climate thermostat?

- Yes... through **long-term** negative feedback mechanisms...
 - **Climate**: higher temperature accelerate weathering → lower CO₂ concentrations
 - **Mountain building**: increases weathering potential and reinforces silicate weathering
 - Young mountain ranges weather more rapidly than older ones, more impact when in warm, humid climates
 - Increased erosion and burial of organic carbon from vegetation

Mineral carbonation as a climate thermostat?

- ... and no... it won't miraculously save our climate:
 - **Very slow** thermostat (period of X00,000 years)
 - Does **not** interfere with intense **short term** climate change, e.g.:
 - Ice age temperature cycling
 - Recent global warming by anthropogenic CO₂ emissions

Temperature changes during Middle and Upper Pleistocene

[Source: NASA Earth Observatory]

Recent temperature rise since 1850

[Source: IPCC AR6, 2021]

Mineral carbonation as CCU approach?

Carbonates as common rock-forming minerals

Composition of the Earth's crust

Elements forming soluble carbonates

Elements forming stable carbonates

Mineral carbonation as CCU approach?

Thermodynamically favorable (yet kinetically constrained)

Stage 1
Natural resources

Stage 2
Portland cement

Stage 3
Concrete structure

Stage 4
Carbonation product

Resources & Carbon Reduction Potential

Resources for mineral carbonation

Recycled resources and wastes

- Cementitious products waste
- Metallurgy slags
- Biomass/coal ashes
- Paper industry waste
- Mining waste

Recycled resource

- Limited associated direct CO₂ emissions
- Local resources – supply constraints
- Environmental compatibility

Manufactured precursors

- Portland cement
- Lime
- Carbonation clinker

Carbonate precursor

- Tailored product
- Production cost
- Process emissions
- Abundant raw materials (limestone, clays)
- No supply constraints

Resources for mineral carbonation

- **Reactivity rules of thumb:**

1. **Cation:** $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Fe}^{2+}$ (mixed cations assume intermediary reactivity)
2. **Anion:** (hydr)oxides > hydrates (silicates/aluminates) > silicates > aluminates/ferrites
3. **Composition:** the higher the content of carbonatable Ca, Mg,... the higher the reactivity towards CO_2 – may also be expressed as moduli, e.g. Ca/Si for calcium silicates

- Reflects **crystal structure** – e.g. silicate framework connectivity
- Largely follows **solubility** trends
- **Surface chemistry** (passivation layers) may limit dissolution and reactivity

[Milani et al. 2021]

CO₂ reduction potential

- High level inventory studies (treat with care):
 - Common assumptions
 - Maximal CO₂ uptake
 - Maximal utilisation of carbonatable waste
 - Presence of infrastructure and markets
 - Low-carbon energy
 - Results
 - **310 Mt CO₂/y** direct reductions globally based on mineralisation of waste (10-fold for indirect savings) (Pan et al. 2020)
 - **160 Mt/y** for Europe, including primary resource mineralisation (Ostovari et al. 2023)
 - Compare
 - Global CO₂ emissions in 2020: **38 Gt**
 - EU cement sector emissions were **110-120 Mt** in 2020

[Pan et al. 2020]

[Ostovari et al. 2023]

Advances in mineral carbonation
science and technology for
production of construction materials

Lecture 2 – Mineral Carbonation Applications

Ruben Snellings, KU Leuven, Belgium
ASCENT Summer School, Zlarin

[Pirrouet bricks – Vandersanden, BE]

Mineral carbonation for cement and concrete - Terminology

Materials and Structures (2025) 58:57
<https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-024-02467-y>

RILEM TC RECOMMENDATION

RILEM TC 309-MCP: recommendation on terminology for mineral carbonation construction products

Ruben Snellings¹ · Thomas Matschei

Why establish terminology?

- Rapidly developing field
- Integration/borrowing of terms from adjacent fields (civil engineering, geochemistry, chemical engineering, etc.)
- Different “schools” using their own terms
- **Mix-up** of terminology
 - One term referring to different things
 - Different terms referring to the same
- Clear need for a **rational, harmonized, consensus-based** terminology

Why establish terminology?

Recommended term	Definition	Synonyms	Notes
Field			
Mineral Carbonation	The reaction of CO ₂ with metal bearing materials to form insoluble, inorganic carbonates, with Ca and Mg being the most common metals. Suitable materials can be abundant silicate rocks or alkaline industrial residues.	CO ₂ Mineralization, Carbon Mineralization	Formation of organic carbon compounds is excluded.
Enforced carbonation	The engineered process used to expedite of the mineral carbonation reaction. This includes extensive preparation of reactant materials, use of elevated CO ₂ concentrations, increase of temperature and pressure, and chemical activation.	Enhanced carbonation	
Accelerated Carbonation	The process used to assess the resistance of a concrete to deterioration by exposure to ambient CO ₂ . The process conditions are specified by standardized testing procedures to accelerate the reaction without significantly changing the reaction mechanism. Typically involves moderately elevated CO ₂ concentrations (e.g. 1-3% CO ₂ and 60% relative humidity at ambient temperature).		

Recommended term	Definition	Synonyms
Processing		
Aqueous Carbonation	Mineral carbonation in aqueous suspensions, or fully saturated conditions with excess aqueous solution	Wet carbonation; liquid-solid carbonation
Moist Carbonation	Mineral carbonation below the water saturation vapor pressure, yet not in fully dry conditions, resulting in partially water saturated porosity and presence of adsorbed water on particle surfaces.	Semi-dry carbonation; semi-wet carbonation
Dry Carbonation	Mineral carbonation in fully dry conditions, usually at elevated temperatures above the boiling point of water.	Gas-solid carbonation
Carbonation Curing	The process used to cure materials under conditions that expedite mineral carbonation, such as elevated CO ₂ concentration, temperature, pressure, etc. Often used with reference to concrete and in contrast to hydration curing.	Carbonation treatment
Carbonation hardening	The process used to solidify or bind a material by mineral carbonation, where the formed carbonates act as cement and fill internal porosity, hence increasing the mechanical strength of the material.	
Direct carbonation	Mineral carbonation in a one-step process involving direct reaction of the metal bearing reagent with CO ₂ leading to simultaneous precipitation of carbonates.	
Indirect carbonation	Multiple step mineral carbonation process where extraction of metals from reagent materials is separated from reaction with CO ₂ and formation of carbonates.	

Recommended term	Definition	Notes
Products		
Carbonatable Binder	Metal bearing material able to react with CO ₂ under industrially applicable conditions to form insoluble carbonates that act as inorganic cementitious binder.	
Carbonated Aggregate	Inert, granular material of sand to gravel size treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation and, as a result of the treatment comprising newly formed, insoluble carbonates. The material has a particle density greater than 2.0 g/cm ³ .	
Carbonated Recycled Concrete Aggregate	Granular material of sand to gravel size obtained through recycling of hardened concrete and treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation to sequester CO ₂ or enhance its performance characteristics. This material mainly consist of natural aggregates and adhered hardened cement paste or mortar.	
Carbonated recycled concrete fines	Granular material of sand size or finer obtained through recycling of hardened concrete and treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation to sequester CO ₂ or enhance its performance characteristics. This material mainly consist of natural fine aggregate (sand) and adhered or liberated hardened cement paste.	(sand + paste)
Carbonated recycled concrete binder	Fine powder obtained through recycling of hardened concrete and treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation to sequester CO ₂ or enhance its performance characteristics. This material mainly consist of liberated hardened cement paste and residual fine aggregate.	Paste (mainly)
Carbonated Lightweight Aggregate	Porous, granular or agglomerated material of sand to gravel size and particle density of less than 2.0 g/cm ³ that is treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation. As a result of the treatment, the material comprises newly formed, insoluble carbonates that may enhance the performance properties of the material.	

TC-MCP terms and definitions

Recommended term	Definition
Products	
Carbonated Supplementary Cementitious Material	Fine material treated by enforced (enhanced) carbonation to sequester CO ₂ and enhance its performance as a reactive supplementary cementitious material for use in cement or concrete.
Carbonated Filler	Fine material treated by enforced carbonation to sequester CO ₂ and enhance its performance as an inert filler material for use in cement or concrete.
Carbonated Block	Pre-shaped, 3-dimensional carbonation hardened product. Carbonates act as main binder.
Carbonation-cured Concrete	Carbonation cured concrete. Carbonates and/or hydrates act as binder.

Recommended term	Definition	Synonyms
KPI		
CO₂ Uptake	Amount of CO ₂ taken up by a material by carbonate formation during a specified carbonation process. Usually taken as the difference between an initial and final state, and expressed on a mass basis, with reference to the initial state.	
Carbonation Potential	<p>The theoretical, maximum attainable CO₂ uptake of a material, considering conversion of all metals in the material that can form insoluble carbonates.</p> <p>For cementitious materials the Steinoor equation is often used, where Ca, Mg, Na and K contents are considered and a sulfate correction is included. Depending on the material and the process, the calculation can be modified.</p>	
Carbonation Rate	Speed at which the carbonation takes places, usually referred to as the uptake or conversion of CO ₂ into solid carbonates over a given time increment. Knowing the reaction stoichiometry, the carbonation rate can also be expressed using the consumption of other reagents or the formation of reaction products.	
Carbonation Degree	The extent to which the mineral carbonation reaction has reached completion. Usually referred to as the ratio of the CO ₂ uptake at a given time over the carbonation potential.	Carbonation Extent
Carbonation Kinetics	The field of research addressing how the carbonation rate is influenced by process conditions, material properties, etc., what this implies for reaction mechanisms, and how this can be modeled.	

Mineral carbonation mechanisms and processes

Mineral carbonation mechanism

- $CO_2 + H_2O \leftrightarrow H_2CO_3$
- $H_2CO_3 \leftrightarrow HCO_3^- + H^+$
- $HCO_3^- \leftrightarrow CO_3^{2-} + H^+$
- $H_2O \leftrightarrow H^+ + OH^-$

- $CaSiO_3 + 2H^+ \leftrightarrow SiO_2 + Ca^{2+} + H_2O$

- $CO_3^{2-} + Ca^{2+} \leftrightarrow CaCO_3$

CO₂ dissolution and aqueous carbonate speciation

Precursor dissolution

Carbonate precipitation

Mineral carbonation mechanism

Aqueous carbonate speciation

Carbonate solubility (pH)

Mineral carbonation mechanism

Aqueous carbonate speciation

Carbonate solubility (T, P)

Carbonation products

Carbonates

- Calcium carbonates
 - Calcite (most stable)
 - Aragonite
 - Vaterite
 - Amorphous calcium carbonate (least stable)
- Minor solid solutions (Ca(Mg), Ca(Fe))
- Magnesium carbonates
 - Magnesite
 - Hydrated magnesium carbonates

Residual phases

- Amorphous (alumina-)silica phase
- Heterogeneity of gel phase of variable Al/Si ratio (depending on precursor chemistry)

[Neto et al. 2024]

Mineral carbonation processing

0

0.1

(0.2)

1

10

Liquid to solid ratio

Dry carbonation

- High T
- With grinding

Moist carbonation

- Partial saturation
- Controlled RH
- Low to mid T and P

Concrete curing

- Saturated
- Low T

Concrete mixing

- Saturated
- Low T

Wet carbonation

- Suspension/slurry
- Range of T and P

Carbon uptake

Activation (SCM,...)

Carbonation hardening

Acceleration of hydration

Activation (SCM,...)

Mineral carbonation products

Aggregates

- RCA
- LWA

Powders

- Fillers, SCMs,...

Shaped end-products (non reinforced)

- Blocks, pavers,...
- Panels, tiles,...
- ...

Recycled concrete aggregates

Materials and Structures

<https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-024-02489-6>

RILEM TC

Carbonated recycled concrete aggregates in construction: potential and bottlenecks identified by RILEM TC 309-MCP

Yury Villagran-Zaccardi ·
Jean Michel Torrenti ·
Theodore Hanein ·
Ruben Snellings

Concrete is coarse and fine aggregates glued together by cement paste

- Presence of microporous hardened cement paste affects RCA quality
 - Higher water absorption (porosity)
 - Lower abrasion/fragmentation resistance
 - Reduced F/T resistance
- Can mineral carbonation be applied to enhance RCA properties?

Adopted from F. Rajabipour

Influence of processing parameters on CO₂ uptake

Size effects

RH

CO₂ concentration

[Fang et al (2017)]

- RCA size: fine RCA contains higher paste content, higher SSA for fine RCA
- Storage conditions: natural carbonation occurs, but only superficially in stockpiles
- Optimum effect for RH – related to facilitation of gaseous transport into the RCA pore structure, while retaining moisture-filled fine porosity for CO₂ dissolution
- **Temperature:**
 - increases carbonation rate, but reduces CO₂ solubility in H₂O
 - Higher T leads to other Cc polymorphs (aragonite, vaterite)
- **CO₂ concentration:** increases rate, yet for RCA at low P no significant benefit beyond 20% CO₂

Effect of saturation degree on RCA carbonation

Accelerated carbonation of wet RCA
[1 bar, 20°C, 24 h]

Accelerated carbonation of dried RCA
[1 bar, 20°C, 24h]

[Gholizadeh et al. 2020]

Effect of saturation degree on RCA carbonation

Saturated conditions

Leaching of Ca^{2+} by moisture release

Non-saturated conditions

Formation of densified CaCO_3 surface layer

[Gholizadeh et al. 2020]

Property modification of cRCA

Solid volume change brought about by carbonation:

$$(\Delta V_{solid} = 12 \text{ vol. \%})$$

$$(\Delta V_{solid} = -13 (?) \text{ vol. \%})$$

$$(\Delta V_{solid} = -48 \text{ vol. \%})$$

Maximum CO₂ uptake does not coincide with maximum porosity reduction or RCA property enhancement!

[Shi et al., 2016]

Property modification of cRCA

- Optimal carbonation processing leads to property enhancement:
 - Density increase (0.5 to 5 rel.%)
 - Porosity decrease (20-30 rel.%)
 - Water absorption reduction (1 to 3 m%)
 - Improved crushing and wear resistance (-20 to -40%)
- Attention points
 - Increases stiffness and shrinkage by porosity refinement and drying → risk on microcracking and related property degradation

RCA surface porosity reduction by carbonation treatment as measured electron microscopy
[Zhan BJ et al., 2019]

Property modification of cRRCF

For optimal carbonation conditions: 0.5 bar CO₂, 80 °C, 30 h

Phase development

[Gholizadeh & Snellings 2022]

Microstructure

Mechanical performance

of fine aggregate fraction!

Carbonated SCMs and fillers

Carbonated fillers and SCMs for cement and concrete

Precursor raw materials

- Natural resources (basic rocks)
 - Basalts, peridotite, serpentinites, (skarns)
- Mining waste (waste rock, tailings)
 - Cr cumulates in peridotites, Pb-Zn-Ag in calcic skarns, diamonds in kimberlite
- Cementitious waste (construction and demolition)
- Ferrous metallurgy slags (steel)
- Incineration and combustion ashes (waste, biomass)
- Artificial carbonation precursors (carbonatable clinker)

[Zajac et al. 2021]

Carbonated fillers and SCMs

Steel slag

Recycled cement paste

[Zajac et al. 2020]

Carbonated SCMs and fillers - composition

Carbonated RCP (Neto et al. 2024)

Carbonated RCP (Zajac et al. 2021)

Carbonated SCMs and fillers - reactivity

- **Alumina-silica gel** shows pozzolanic reactivity
 - High SSA → high early reactivity / heat release in R3 tests
 - Consumption of Ca(OH)_2 in blended cements

R3 test of carbonated ferro-nickel slag [Cyr et al.]

R3 test of carbonated recycled cement pastes [Neto et al., 2024]

Ca(OH)_2 consumption of carbonated recycled cement pastes [Zajac et al., 2021]

Carbonated SCMs and fillers - reactivity

- **Alumina-silica gel** shows pozzolanic reactivity
 - Rapid consumption of alumina-silica gel observed by NMR in blended cements and R3 pastes

[Zajac et al., 2023]

[Neto et al., 2024]

Carbonated SCMs and fillers - reactivity

- Reaction products in blended cements:
 - Pozzolanic reaction
 - $AS\text{-gel} + Ca(OH)_2 \rightarrow C\text{-(A)-S-H}$
 - Redistribution of Al from high A/S ratio AS-gel into C-(A)-S-H (lower A/S ratio) and AFm
 - C-A-S-H chain length is observed to decrease with curing age of blended cements
 - Carbo-aluminate reaction
 - $AFm\text{-CO}_3$ (hemi- and monocarbonate)

[Zajac et al., 2023]

Carbonated SCMs and fillers

- Early age performance of cement and concrete containing cSCMs is affected by:

1. High SSA
2. Presence of fine carbonates: filler effect (C-S-H nucleation)
3. Rapid pozzolanic reaction
4. Ions leached during early hydration

- Workability/water demand:

- Generally higher than PC or conventional SCMs (GGBFS, FA)
- Carbonation may lower water demand of certain ashes or slags containing free lime
- Increased superplasticiser dosage or slump retention and retarding admixtures can be used to compensate

- Setting time:

- Usually shorter than reference cements (high fineness, nucleation, rapid pozzolanic reaction)
- Some carbonated slags and ashes present longer setting times due to leaching of ions (e.g. Zn, Pb,...) that delay or perturb cement hydration

Carbonated SCMs and fillers

- Compressive strength
 - Early age strength contribution by:
 - Filler effect of fine carbonates
 - Pozzolanic reaction of the alumina-silica gel
 - Continuous strength increase till late age

Mineral carbonation products

Aggregates

- RCA
- LWA

Powders

- Fillers, SCMs,...

Shaped end-products (non reinforced)

- Blocks, pavers,...
- Panels, tiles,...
- ...

CO₂ hardened preshaped products

- **Precursors:**

- Carbonation clinkers
- Recycled concrete waste
- Steel slags
- ...

- **Processing:**

- Usually moist carbonation curing
- Conditions depending on precursor and product

- **CO₂ uptake:**

- Process and precursor dependent
- Typically 50-150 kg CO₂/t of product

- **Products:**

- Bricks and blocks
- Pavers and tiles
- Slates and sheets
- ...

- **References:**

- Carbstone/Vandersanden
- Carbicrete
- CarbonBuilt
- ...

CO₂ hardening - carbonation mechanism and microstructure

- Reactive transport process
 - CO₂ diffuses inwards, through gas phase (CO₂ dissolution and diffusion in water is slower)
 - H₂O transported outwards
- Open porosity/partial saturation
 - Low workability
 - Vibration/compaction molded
- Low alkalinity
 - Not compatible with steel reinforcement (?)
- Carbonates, not hydrates:
 - Higher strength/product ratio
 - More brittle/stiff mechanical behaviour

CO₂ hardening - effect of process parameters on CO₂ uptake

Effect of fineness

[20 bar, 80°C, 100% CO₂]

Effect of compaction pressure

[20 bar, 140°C, 100% CO₂]

Effect of CO₂ gas purity

[20 bar, 20°C, 175 kgf/cm²]

[Quaghebeur et al., 2015]

CO₂ hardening – microstructural aspects

- BUT... different conditions and precursors affect carbonate vs. performance relationships

CO₂ hardening - effect of temperature on microstructure

Low temperature (10-20°C):

- High CO₂ solubility
- Slow dissolution of Ca²⁺
- Precipitation at precursor surfaces
- Denser microstructure, bridging particles
- Larger capillary pores

High temperature (60°C):

- Low CO₂ solubility
- More rapid dissolution of Ca²⁺
- Precipitation in aqueous phase
- Matrix filled more homogeneously
- Smaller capillary pores

[Nielsen et al. 2019]

CO₂ hardening - effect of slag precursor

- BOF carbon steel slag

- Carbonatable phases: Ca(OH)₂, C₂S, C₃AH₆
- Hydroxides carbonate rapidly and completely
- Volume gain is 10-20 vol.%
- Microporous microstructure
- Lower MPa/CO₂ uptake ratio

- EAF stainless steel slag

- Carbonatable phases: C₂S, merwinite, bredigite, cuspidine
- Silicates carbonate more slowly and incompletely
- Volume gain around 70 vol% (for γ-C₂S)
- Higher MPa/CO₂ uptake ratio

[Librandi et al. 2019]

	Hydroxides e.g. portlandite (CH), brucite	Ca(Mg) silicates e.g. C ₂ S, merwinite, bredigite
Before carbonation		
After carbonation		
SEM-BSE image		

Conclusions and perspectives

- Mineral carbonation is **gaining traction** as a way to produce low-carbon and carbon-negative construction materials: aggregates, SCMs, blocks, tiles,...
- **Dry, moist, wet carbonation processes** developed – depending on carbonatable precursor and targeted product.
- **Wide range** of applications and products under development and, locally, entering the market
- **Perspectives** for research and development
 - Need for new **test methods, terminology** and **impact** data
 - High potential for **research** to better understand underlying **mechanisms, material behavior** and **durability**.
 - Very high potential for **development** of new and better **processes and products**.

Advances in mineral carbonation science and technology for production of construction materials

Lecture 3 – Characterization techniques

Ruben Snellings, KU Leuven, Belgium
ASCENT Summer School, Zlarin

Introduction

- How to evaluate the efficiency of mineral carbonation processes?
- How to assess the CO₂ footprint or CO₂ offset of mineral carbonation products?
- Key performance indicators?
 - **CO₂ uptake**
 - **Degree of carbonation**
 - Mechanical performance (e.g. compressive strength)
 - (Effect on) workability – water demand
 - Microstructure – porosity – water absorption
 - Durability indicators
 - ...

Characterisation techniques

Determination of CO₂ content in solids

Characterisation techniques

Calcimetry

- Wet-chemical method
- Principle: digestion in acid to release bound CO_2 in sample
- Measurement by:
 - Volumetric analysis of evolved gas
 - Manometry (pressure build-up)
 - Acid titration of precipitated BaCO_3 + indicator

Calcimeter measuring the CO_2 volume released

Digestion + titration analysis

[Courtesy of S. Braymand]

Characterisation techniques

Calcimetry

- Pros:
 - Affordable setup
 - Relatively fast
- Cons:
 - Requires trained personnel
 - Not all carbonates are easily digested in acid (e.g. Ca-Mg carbonates, Fe-carbonates,...)
 - No information on carbonate type
 - High error for low contents of CO_2

Calcimeter measuring the CO_2 volume released

Digestion + titration analysis

[Courtesy of S. Braymand]

Characterisation techniques

Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetric Analysis measures the mass of a substance as a function of temperature or time as the sample specimen is subjected to a controlled temperature program in a controlled atmosphere (N_2 , CO_2 ...).

- Detects weight loss or weight gain due to:
 - Decomposition, combustion, oxidation,...
- Weight change over defined temperature interval can be equated to phase content or bound H_2O , CO_2 ...

Characterisation techniques

Thermogravimetric analysis

- Pros:
 - Straightforward
 - Relatively accessible
 - Small sample size
 - Simultaneous measurement of bound water, ignited mass,...
- Cons:
 - Overlap of thermal events
 - Small sample size
 - Relatively long measurements

Carbonate thermal decomposition ranges

Formula	Mineral/phase	Decarbonation range (°C)*
CaCO ₃	Calcite	650-900
CaCO ₃	Aragonite	Transforms to calcite at 400-550 °C
CaCO ₃	Vaterite	Transforms to Cc at 400-550 °C
CaCO ₃ .xH ₂ O	Amorph. CaCO ₃	Transforms to Cc at 350-500 °C
CaMg(CO ₃) ₂	Dolomite	600-850
MgCO ₃	Magnesite	500-600
FeCO ₃	Siderite	300-500

*range shifts depending on measurement conditions, sample crystallinity, crystallite size

Characterisation techniques

Combustion analysis (CS analyser)

- Principle: oxidative combustion of carbon and carbonates, detection of CO₂ in evolved gas stream (e.g. by IR)
- Pros:
 - Rapid and straightforward technique
 - Relatively affordable and accessible
 - Accuracy and precision
 - Small sample size
- Cons:
 - No distinction between organic and inorganic carbon
 - Small sample size

Characterisation techniques

Vibrational spectroscopy – FTIR

- Interaction of IR light with molecular vibration (absorption – dipole change)

Anti-symmetric stretching vibration at 2349 cm^{-1}

Anti-symmetric stretching vibration at 3756 cm^{-1}

Phase	Chemical Formula	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	ν_4
Calcite	CaCO_3	-	874	1420	713 w
Aragonite	CaCO_3	1083	844/854	1461	700/712
Vaterite	CaCO_3	1087 w	876	1476	744 w
Amorphous Calcium Carbonate	$\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1067	864	1492	690/725 w
Monohydrocalcite		1063 w	872	1492	698
Ikaite		1085 w	876	1425 w	720 w

Peaks which are typically weak are identified with a 'w'. Exact numbers are variable, and a good summary is provided in [11,13].

Characterisation techniques

X-ray diffraction applied to mineral carbonation research

- **Pros**
 - Accessible and straightforward
 - Identification and quantification of various carbonate minerals (and other crystalline phases)
 - Follow-up on total amorphous content
- **Cons**
 - Expertise required for in-depth analysis
 - No direct quantification of CO₂ content
 - Accuracy/precision depends on analyst experience

[Courtesy of D. Jansen]

Characterisation techniques

Solid state NMR

- Chemical shift of NMR signal reflects elemental bonding environment
- Does not depend on crystallinity, also informs on amorphous phases
- Element specific (^1H , ^{13}C , ^{27}Al , ^{29}Si)
- Quantitative
- Drawbacks
 - Expertise required to run instruments
 - Accessibility, cost
 - Measurement times can be long (e.g. ^{29}Si)

[Courtesy of J. Skibsted]

Key take-aways

- CO₂ uptake measurements is main KPI of mineral carbonation processes and products
- CO₂ uptake = difference pre- and post- process/stage
- Various measurement techniques can be used – important to know method-specific limitations, interferences
- Attention to be paid to sampling materials displaying heterogeneous carbonation degree
- Calculation of CO₂ uptake (m%) requires correction for other reactions change sample mass